

Centralized DC Voltage Control for a Multiport Converter in Distribution Grids

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Abstract

Power electronics components are becoming essential for smart grids, especially integrating systems such as renewable energies, storage or electric vehicles. Multiport converters are presented as a solution to reduce the cost of installing individual power electronic devices and integrating multiple AC and DC systems. This paper proposes a centralized DC voltage control for non-isolated Multiport converters with a common DC bus. Such control is designed for a proper dynamic response in normal operation and AC fault-ride through capability. The centralized DC voltage control is validated in three- and four-port converters, where AC ports are connected to two feeders of the same distribution AC grid. DC ports are connected to a battery or DC load. Time-domain simulations in Matlab Simulink are used to test the presented control strategy in several case studies.

Keywords: Multiport converters, DC voltage control, Control design, Fault-ride through.

1. Introduction

The integration of distributed renewable generation in the grid is driving an increase in power electronic devices [1]. As a result, the design and operation of the distribution grid are changing, leading to new technical challenges related to line and transformer overloads, voltage regulation, fault protection and power quality [1, 2, 3]. These issues are traditionally addressed by building new lines and transformers, but this option might not be preferred due to the environmental impact, social opposition and high cost. An alternative option is to maximize

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the use of existing grid infrastructure. In this direction, installing power electronic devices, such as Voltage Source Converters (VSC), is a potential solution. The grid operation could be improved by installing storage components or improving the flexibility of VSC-connected renewable generation [4]. Multiport converters (MC) are an alternative solution with multiple AC and DC ports in one device [5]. This converter structure has been originally proposed in [6, 7]. A port is defined as a set of terminals that satisfies the port-Kirchoff current law, as described in [8]. Fig. 1 shows a conceptual example of an MC with three AC ports and three DC ports.

Figure 1: Conceptual representation of an MC with multiple AC and DC ports.

MCs are aimed to reduce the total number of power electronics components or their total size, i.e. the total cost. At high voltage (HV) and medium voltage (MV) MCs are an interesting option to decrease number of AC-DC converters to connect HVDC or MVDC systems to HVAC grids [9]. At MV and particularly at low voltage (LV) levels, the presented applications are mainly focused on DC grids with DC ports connected with a common DC bus [10, 11], as MCs could simplify the integration of energy storage systems. MCs are also expected to increase grid utilization by changing the power flows [12], e.g. when lines are overloaded [13], and to increase grid resiliency by supplying energy to islanded systems after a contingency [14].

MCs can be classified into two main topologies: isolated and non-isolated configurations. MCs with two isolated ports are known as Solid State Transformers (SSTs) [15], while non-isolated MCs with two ports are named Soft Open Points (SOPs) [16, 17]. In this article, a non-isolated MC at LV level is analysed.

Non-isolated MCs typically have a DC bus to interconnect all the ports. Then, the DC bus voltage regulation is essential to ensure that all ports can remain connected and exchange power. If the DC bus of a MC is not properly regulated, the connected DC loads may experience adverse effects. In addition, the DC grid could operate outside its appropriate voltage range. In the literature, most of the DC voltage control strategies that can be used for MCs have

been presented for DC grid applications, especially in DC microgrids [18] and High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) grids [19]. In these cases, two control structures are typically used: leader-follower [20] and distributed DC voltage control [21]. A conventional leader-follower, also known as master-slave, strategy is presented in [20], where one AC port controls the DC bus voltage and reactive power while the other port controls the active and reactive powers [20]. However, if an AC fault is located near the leader port the DC grid voltage regulation is compromised. Consequently, robustness with AC faults in conventional leader-follower configuration is not guaranteed. On the other hand, distributed DC voltage control strategies have been presented in the literature to overcome the leader-follower control limitations [22, 23]. In this case, the most used strategies are Voltage Margin Method (VMM) [22] and droop control [23]. VMM controls the DC voltage inside a defined margin [22]. However, in a DC grid, VMM may not ensure DC voltage regulation at the nominal value and in case of a large number of DC terminals, the implementation is complex and may be unfeasible. Droop control consists of a DC voltage proportional controller, which modifies the power (measured at the converter’s AC or DC part) [24] or the DC current [25]. Therefore, droop control can be implemented at various DC grid terminals to regulate DC voltage and share DC power or current among the terminals [26]. Despite this, notice that droop control still results in an error at the DC voltage magnitudes. Communications could improve the voltage regulation in DC grids [27], but total costs would increase.

In SOPs, controller solutions are similar to DC grids. Leader-follower control is a widely used strategy [16], although the limitations inherent in DC grids persist. Distributed DC voltage control strategies such as droop control and VMM are also featured in SOPs [28, 29], showing the same benefits and limitations as those observed with DC grids. In the particular case of MCs controllers, the authors have presented a VMM for a non-isolated MC with two AC ports and one DC port [30]. However, VMM cannot guarantee accurate tracking and is not easily scalable to N ports. As MCs are single devices with AC and DC ports connected together with a common DC bus, i.e. they are not separated by DC lines as in DC grids, a centralized control solution without communications is the preferred option. A centralized control architecture has been presented with DC MCs in [31]. The solution proposed in [31] employs a centralized control approach for DC voltage, achieving precise regulation. However, this control architecture may require a redesign if port connections are modified. Another drawback is that the proposed solution in [31] does not consider the inclusion of AC ports. Alternative solutions proposed in the literature, such as those in [6, 32], incorporate AC ports; however, they do not address power dispatch strategies or fault ride-through capabilities. Additionally in [31], the active power dispatch of the ports has not been studied under varying AC grid conditions, such as AC faults or unbalances. Therefore, effective controller solutions for AC operating N-port MCs have not been presented in the literature. This paper presents a centralized DC voltage control for non-isolated MCs to ensure adequate DC bus voltage regulation in normal and fault operation. The proposed control architecture has the following contributions:

- Flexible solution that can be implemented for multiple number of ports. In the literature, droop control is also adequate for multiple DC terminals, but presents DC voltage regulation error. Flexible solutions with AC and DC ports have been found in the literature, but are not robust against AC faults.
- Accurate DC bus voltage regulation. In contrast to the VMM and the droop control, a zero steady-state error is obtained. The leader-follower approach can also achieve accurate regulation, but in case the leader port is not available, DC voltage controllability is lost. Centralized controllers in the literature demonstrate accurate DC bus voltage regulation. However, they are not easily adaptable to different port connections.
- Robust control architecture against AC faults. The remaining ports unaffected by AC faults can maintain control functionalities without MC disconnection. In the literature, VMM and droop control can also be robust against AC faults, but without ensuring an accurate DC voltage regulation.

In normal operation, the centralized DC voltage control is designed based on linearized models and applying an optimization problem with H_∞ norm to obtain the control gains. In fault operation, the general control structure is modified to ensure DC voltage regulation in case of AC faults at any MC port. The proposed DC voltage control is tested in a LV distribution system with two feeders, where MCs with three and five ports are connected at the end of the feeders. Time-domain simulations in Matlab-Simulink are considered to validate the MC control.

2. Multiport Converter Architecture and Control

This section presents the MC architecture used in this article and the required control structure for normal operation in the AC and DC ports.

Figure 2: Topologies of the MC ports.

2.1. Converter Topology and Modelling Assumptions

The topology studied is a non-isolated configuration with a common DC bus, where the AC ports are two level voltage source converter (2L-VSC) AC-DC converters and the DC ports are boost DC-DC converters or output terminals

for elements directly connected to the DC bus. The structure of both topologies are illustrated in Fig. 2. Fig. 3 shows an example of an LV grid with MCs, where the MC is employed to interconnect LV AC feeders and to interface with a DC grid.

Figure 3: Example of MC application in a LV grid.

The converter representation is based on average models, i.e. without including the switching operation of the ports, which is enough to capture the dynamic response defined by the port control. A transformer, placed between the converter and the AC grid, provides isolation. The transformer is not explicitly represented in the circuit diagram, as the system is modeled in p.u. values, with the transformer represented by its series impedance. Consequently, due to the presence of the transformer and the configuration of the system as a balanced three-wire network, no zero-sequence current flows through the AC system. Therefore, on the AC side, the converter ports are modelled with a three-phase controlled voltage source and a series RL system, where L_c represents the inductance of the filter and the transformer, and R_c represents the equivalent resistance. A representation of a model on the AC side with one feeder is illustrated in Fig. 4. L_g represents the inductance of the Thevenin of the grid and the transformer, while R_g is the equivalent resistance. The voltage and current measurements, v_g and i_s , are taken at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC).

Figure 4: Model of the AC side.

In the model, the DC ports are represented as a separate circuit incorporating a controlled voltage source connected to the corresponding DC elements. The battery is modeled as a DC voltage source, while the loads are represented by resistors. Additionally, another circuit is used to represent the common DC bus. All converter ports, both AC and DC, are modeled as controlled current sources connected to a common DC bus with a capacitor. The currents applied at the current source are given by

$$i_{dc}^n = \frac{P_{dc}^n}{v_{dc}}, \quad (1)$$

where n defines the port number. For the AC ports, the losses between the active power supplied by the converter, P_c , and the DC power are assumed to be negligible.

A three-port MC is analysed in this paper (as seen in Fig. 6), but also a five-port MC is tested in Section V to validate that the presented control structure can be used for a higher number of ports. Therefore, Fig. 5 shows the equivalent circuit model for the five-port MC.

Figure 5: Average circuit model.

2.2. General Control Structure

The objectives of the control structure presented in this article depend on the operation conditions: normal and fault operation. As this article is not focus on fault detection, a fault detection algorithm is not included. Instead, a 10 ms delay is assumed to represent the fault detection time.

In normal operation, the converter must ensure:

- Power flow exchange among the ports according to the desired power references.
- Voltage regulation of the common DC bus.

In case of AC faults, the converter must ensure:

- AC fault-ride-through capability, i.e. remaining connected to the AC grid during faults and injecting support fault current.
- Converter current saturation, i.e. the ports operate within safe current limits.
- DC bus voltage regulation by the available ports, i.e. the ports that are not affected by the faults have to maintain their control capabilities.

Fig. 6 shows an example of the general control structure in a 3-ports converter and the control details of AC and DC ports are presented in Fig. 7 and 8, respectively. The control architecture presented in Fig. 6 is valid for N-ports converters, where the additional ports can be also AC-DC and DC-DC converters.

Figure 6: MC control structure with a possible structure of 3-ports.

The AC port control is a cascaded control with a PLL, an active power control and an inner current control. The control is implemented in a qd reference frame, where q component represents the active power current, and d component the reactive current [4]. This choice isn't common and perhaps should be

highlighted somewhere in the text to avoid misunderstandings. Also, a positive-negative sequence control is considered to ensure proper operation for balanced and unbalanced faults. The qd positive and negative sequence components are obtained using a filter that approximates the Hilbert transformation [33]. The Hilbert transform functions as a notch filter at 100 Hz, ensuring that the sequences are uncoupled after Park transforms. If not, in unbalanced conditions, both positive and negative sequences will contain 100 Hz components, which the PI controllers would be unable to handle effectively. The reference of the negative sequence currents is 0, as assumed in [34].

Figure 7: AC port control.

The DC port controller is a cascaded control as with AC ports, considering only DC components.

Figure 8: DC port control.

The centralized control block regulates the DC voltage bus ensuring that all the ports have to give support proportionally to its nominal active power. Section 3 explains in depth the control scheme.

In the following subsections, the control structure and design of the control architectures required in AC and DC ports for normal operation are explained in more detail. For fault operation, the control structures have to be modified and a fault current injection block and saturations as observed in Fig. 7 are

required, as described in Section 4.

2.2.1. Active Power Control

To control the active power both AC and DC ports apply a reference current calculation, obtaining i_q^{*+} and I_c^* as:

$$i_q^{*+} = \frac{2 P^*}{3 v_q}, I_c^* = \frac{P^*}{v_{DC}}. \quad (2)$$

where P^* is the reference powers obtained from the centralized control, v_q is the q-component of the AC voltage and v_{DC} is the DC voltage measurement. A common approach in AC-DC converters involves using a PI controller for active power control. However, this article proposes an open-loop solution to prevent interactions with the centralized control.

2.2.2. Reactive Power Control

This controller is only used in the AC ports. In normal operation, the reactive power control is based on a PI controller which could ensure reference tracking. The PI controller output is the current reference i_d^{+*} . In fault operation, the PI control structure is combined with a fault current injection block and an anti-windup loop, as explained in Section 4.1. The PI controller gains, K_p^Q and K_i^Q , are designed using the Internal Model Control (IMC) technique described in [4, 35]. The gains are

$$K_p^Q = \frac{\tau_{cl}}{\tau_Q} \cdot \frac{2}{3V_p}; K_i^Q = \frac{1}{\tau_Q} \cdot \frac{2}{3V_p}, \quad (3)$$

where τ_{cl} is the closed loop time constant of the electrical system, τ_Q the time constant of the reactive power and V_p is the peak voltage of the AC grid.

2.2.3. Inner Current Control

Inner current control is used in AC and DC ports. The DC ports require a single PI controller for the DC current. In AC ports, the control structure used is a double-crossed scheme with PI controllers, 2 for the positive sequence and 2 for the negative sequence [34]. It should be noted that the positive sequence current references will be saturated following the strategy defined in Section 4.2. Negative sequence current references are not saturated because are defined as 0. The structure of the inner current control for the AC port is shown in Fig. 9, based on [35]. The control is also designed with IMC technique, as explained in more detail for AC ports in [4, 35]. The proportional and integral gains, K_p^{cl} and K_i^{cl} are

$$K_p^{cl} = \frac{L_l}{\tau_{cl}}; K_i^{cl} = \frac{R_l}{\tau_{cl}}, \quad (4)$$

where τ_{cl} is the closed loop time constant of the electrical system, L_l the inductance of the coupling and R_l the resistance of the coupling. For the DC ports, the structure of the Inner current control is a simple PI. The applied design of the control is equivalent to the AC ports.

Figure 9: Inner current control for the AC port.

2.2.4. PLL

It should be noted that the MC is working in grid-following mode, consequently, a PLL is used to estimate the grid angle and synchronise the ports with the grid [36]. The structure of the PLLs is a closed-loop system with a PI controller. The PLL structure and the modifications done to handle fault operation are shown in Section 4.3. The PI controller is designed with the IMC technique explained in [4, 35]. The gains, K_p^{PLL} and K_i^{PLL} are

$$K_P^{PLL} = \frac{4\xi^2}{\tau_{PLL}V_p}; K_I^{PLL} = \frac{4\xi^2}{\tau_{PLL}^2V_p}, \quad (5)$$

where ξ is the damping ratio, τ_{PLL} the time constant of the PLL and V_p the peak voltage of the AC grid.

3. Centralized DC Voltage Control

This section presents the details of the centralized DC bus voltage control, which is indicated in Fig. 6 and shown in detail in Fig. 10.

3.1. Control Structure

The presented control is based on a PI controller, where the active power reference output P_i^* is distributed to all controllable ports, i.e. ports that are connected through an AC or DC port, as shown in Fig. 10. The power distribution is defined based on the weighting parameters α_i , which represent the contribution of each port to the DC voltage regulation. Therefore, the DC voltage is considered as a scalar variable that represents the power balance of the whole MC. Therefore, the PI controller and α_i gains must be correctly tuned to ensure that in steady state, the active power references $P_{0,i}^*$ are tracked. The weighting parameters α_i should ensure the condition $\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \alpha_i = 1$, where $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the port number of the MC and N is the total number of ports. The active power references are constrained to their nominal values to ensure compliance with manufacturer specifications and grid code requirements. Without this saturation, the centralized control could potentially provide references exceeding the nominal power of the ports, which could lead to operate outside the limits of the port. It is critical that the active power saturation is more

restrictive than the current saturation. Otherwise, the margin to accommodate reactive power could be insufficient. Besides, an anti-windup control is included in the PI controller in case the port powers are saturated [37, 38].

Figure 10: Scheme of centralized DC voltage control.

The α_i calculation is defined based on Algorithm 1. The code prioritizes the ports with DC power supply systems to maintain the DC bus voltage. When DC power supply systems are not available (e.g. due to device failure or low state of charge), the code considers the existence of faults. If there are no faults the code calculates the parameter directly with the nominal active power of each port. On the other hand, when there is a fault, the calculation of the α_i parameter is based on the product between the normalized voltage seen by each port and its nominal active power. In the specific scenario in which a deep fault affects all the ports, the code calculates the parameter as in the case where no faults exist.

Algorithm 1: Algorithm to obtain α_i

input : Available active power of the DC power supply system $P_{DC,i}$, nominal active power of the ports P_i , AC voltages at the ports v_i

output: Weighting parameters α_i

```

1 begin
2   if the DC power supply system is available then
3      $\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{DC,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^M |P_{DC,i}|}$ ;
4   else
5     if no faults exist or there is a port with  $V_i = 0$  then
6        $\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^M |P_{N,i}|}$ ;
7     if a fault exists then
8        $\alpha_i = \frac{\frac{|v_i|}{|V_{N,i}|} |P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{|v_j|}{|V_{N,i}|} |P_{N,i}|}$ ;

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As mentioned, Algorithm 1 design ensures that available DC power supply systems have priority to maintain DC bus voltage stability. The value of α_i is calculated in this case as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{DCi}|}{\sum_{j=1}^{Mdc} |P_{DCi}|}, \quad (6)$$

where P_{DCi} is the active power of the i DC power supply system, and Mdc is the total number of available ports with DC supply.

On the other hand, AC faults are analysed if a DC power supply system connected to the common DC bus does not exist. When no faults exist or all the ports observe a deep fault ($V_i = 0$) the value of the α_i parameter of each port is

$$\alpha_i = \frac{|P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^{Mf} |P_{N,i}|}, \quad (7)$$

where $P_{N,i}$ is the nominal active power of the port i , and Mf is the total number of ports.

When no faults exist and at least one port is far enough from a fault ($v_i \neq 0$), the value of α_i is

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\frac{|v_i|}{|V_{N,i}|} |P_{N,i}|}{\sum_{j=1}^M \frac{|v_j|}{|V_{N,i}|} |P_{N,i}|}, \quad (8)$$

where v_i is the voltage measurement of the port i , M the total number of ports and $V_{N,i}$ the nominal voltage of the port i .

The application of (8) ensures that the ports with the highest contribution on regulating the DC bus have the most available margin. Consequently, by using Algorithm 1, the control automatically adapts to different AC conditions and DC ports connections. Section 5 shows the functioning of Algorithm 1 in different operation conditions.

3.2. Controller Design

This section presents the design of the PI controller used in the centralized DC voltage control. The PI controller is designed for disturbance rejection against active power variations from the ports $P_{0,i}^*$. Therefore, the AC and DC grids and the controller of the MC (without the centralized control) are defined as the plant of the system. The output of the plant is the DC bus voltage v_{DC} , while the inputs are the active powers obtained from the centralized control P_i^* , the reactive power references Q_i^* , the grid voltage U_{TH} and the grid frequency ω .

Linearized models valid around an equilibrium point are considered to simplify the design. The plant defines the dynamics of the electrical circuit and all the control structure except the PI controller of the centralized control and the α_i gains. Reactive power references, grid voltage, and grid frequency are all set to zero, except for the active power values, which are calculated as shown in Fig. 11. It is important to note that the variation of the active power is directly

the control signal, u , multiplied by the α_i gain, as the operating point of the active powers are equal to their references in steady state.

Figure 11: Model of the system created for the controller design.

The validation of the model is done with a 2 AC ports MC. The complete linear model with the defined plant and the centralized controller has 16 states, 8 inputs and 15 outputs. The implementation of the complete linearized model in Fig. 11 is validated against the non-linear model by modifying the active power references, ΔP_1^* and ΔP_2^* , by 1% of their nominal values in two separate simulations, as illustrated in Fig. 12. In this case, the PI controller parameters of the DC bus voltage control have been initially selected following a trial-and-error approach. It is worth mentioning that the selection of these parameters has neither been quick nor intuitive. Therefore, a more efficient strategy is needed for controller design. With the validated linear plant, the controllability and the observability are checked using the methodology presented in [39] to ensure that the design is possible.

(a) Scenario 1: Port 1 changing active power reference P_0^* . (b) Scenario 2: Port 2 changing active power reference P_1^* .

Figure 12: DC voltage comparison between linearized and non-linearized model with $K_p = 600$ and $K_i = 2500$.

The PI controller is tuned to regulate the DC voltage against active power variations from the ports. In addition, the following specifications are defined:

- Minimum damping ratio of $\sqrt{2}/2$.
- A settling time of at least 0.45 s.

An optimization problem with H_∞ norm is considered to calculate the PI controller parameters that satisfy the previous specifications. This methodology ensures optimal controller performance by effectively attenuating disturbances [40]. By employing this approach, variations in active power can be effectively mitigated, while achieving tracking performance that adheres closely to the specified damping and settling time requirements [40]. The problem formulation includes both hard and soft requirements. The hard requirement is the attenuation of disturbances, specifically active power references $P_{0,i}^*$. As a result, the solver guarantees solutions that satisfy this condition. The soft requirements enable the solver to find solutions that approximate these specifications as closely as possible. In this article, the settling time and the damping ratio are defined as soft requirements.

This process is implemented using MATLAB's *syntune* command, which solves multiple optimization problems based on the given specifications. Appendix A provides a detailed explanation of the optimization problems addressed. These problems are solved using non-convex and non-smooth optimization algorithms as described in [41, 42]. Additionally, the H_∞ norm of the linear model is computed using the two-step algorithm presented in [43]. This algorithm calculates the H_∞ norm of a linear system by determining the maximum singular value, achieving high precision in just two iterations. Fig. 13 illustrates the eigenvalues (closed-loop poles) of the system matrix for the closed-loop linear model under various specified conditions.

Figure 13: Closed-loop poles w.r.t some specifications of the PI centralized controller.

In Fig. 14, the dynamic responses of the derived specifications are compared with those of the trial-and-error (*T&E*) proportional-integral (PI) controller applied to the nonlinear model. The test involves transitioning from 1 p.u. of active power to 0 p.u. at $t=3$ s, to verify that the control design remains valid beyond the small-signal linear model, i.e. considering a non-linear model. The fastest dynamic response is observed when a settling time lower than 0.45 s is defined. The damping ratio specification does not have an important effect on the design, as two conjugated eigenvalues have a damping of 0.696 that is not affected by the centralized controller PI design. Therefore, the designed control has a settling time of 0.45 s and a damping ratio of 0.696. It should be mentioned that *T&E* strategy results are acceptable, but are obtained after a long iteration process, which is far to be efficient. Furthermore, with this strategy, desired specifications are hard to accomplish and optimal results cannot be ensured.

Figure 14: v_{DC} dynamics with different PI specifications.

4. AC Fault-ride Through Control

This section presents the additional control blocks to ensure that the MC can provide fault-ride-through (FRT) capability, i.e. the MC remains connected during faults at the AC ports while the other ports maintain normal operation. The modified elements are:

- Reactive power control block.
- Current references.
- PLL.
- Active power references.

Also, these modifications must ensure an adequate dynamic response, especially after the temporary AC faults are cleared. Reactive power control, Fault Current Injection and modified PLL have already been presented by the authors in another publication [30]. The faults are represented by a signal named *Fault*, which is assumed to have a delay of 10 ms, as mentioned in Section 2.2.

4.1. Fault Current Injection and Reactive Power Control Modification

To maintain the stability of the system, current is injected during the faults. In the grid codes, no limitations in which current has to be injected are presented, although reactive current is normally used when faults have to be isolated [44]. Therefore, to ensure FRT capabilities reactive current is injected. The reactive control part has a sample and hold (S&H) block to freeze the value of the reactive current when a fault occurs, as Fig. 15 shows.

Figure 15: Reactive power control and Fault injection block.

This frozen value is used in the Fault Current Injection block to calculate the value of the injection current according to the $i - v_g^{qd+}$ characteristics. Such attributes are based on the following piece-wise function:

$$\begin{cases} v_g^{low} \leq v_g^{qd+} \leq v_g^{high} \rightarrow & i_{inj}^+ = \Delta i \frac{v_g^{high} - v_g^{qd+}}{v_g^{high} - v_g^{low}} \\ v_g^{qd+} \leq v_g^{low} \rightarrow & i_{inj}^+ = \Delta i \\ v_g^{qd+} \geq v_g^{high} \rightarrow & i_{inj}^+ = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where i_{max} is the maximum port current (typically an overcurrent of 105-110% is considered), v_g^{qd+} is the AC grid voltage and v_g^{low} and v_g^{high} are the voltage limits to define the maximum and minimum current contributions. The reactive power block uses an anti-windup structure to ensure that after a fault the dynamics are not affected by the accumulated error of the PI.

4.2. Current Saturation Strategy

The outputs of the active and reactive power control blocks are the current values in qd^+ reference for each port, which have to be saturated to ensure that

the applied current is always inside the capability of each port. The qd^- current references are always directly 0.

The current limit values i_{low}^{d+} and i_{up}^{d+} , shown in Fig. 15, are the maximum and minimum values the current references could achieve. i_{low}^{d+} and i_{up}^{d+} have to be lower or equal to i_{max} , as it is the limit of the port. In this article, i_{max} is defined as 1.05 times the nominal current of the converters. If the total current equals i_{max} a strategy must be defined to decide which component (q or d) has priority. Therefore, the values for the prioritized and the non-prioritized currents are

$$-i_{max} \leq i_{pr} \leq i_{max}, \quad (10)$$

$$-\sqrt{i_{max}^2 - i_{pr}^2} \leq i_{non-pr} \leq \sqrt{i_{max}^2 - i_{pr}^2}. \quad (11)$$

In this article, following the grid codes [46], the reactive current defined by the d component always has priority. However, when a fault is seen by all the AC ports and no DC power supply systems are available, the less affected AC port prioritizes the q component. Following this strategy, the stability of the DC bus is prioritized.

Grid codes and standards [45, 46] recommend that when the voltage seen by a port is lower than 30% of its nominal value, the port has to be disconnected. And, when the voltage is bigger than 35% of its nominal value, the reference currents are again the calculated values obtained by the controller. This article examines whether a properly designed control system is sufficient to ensure that ports remain connected, even when voltages approach zero. Maintaining these connections allows the exchange of active power, which is critical for stabilizing the DC bus voltage. Additionally, avoiding disconnection eliminates the need for reconnection, which requires higher power consumption. Reconnection can pose risks, specially when the generation connected to the distribution grid is substantial. In such cases, reconnections may lead to frequency unstabilities. Therefore, the simulations presented in this article ensure that ports remain connected, even under conditions of near-zero voltage.

4.3. PLL Modification

In this article, the PLL is modified to avoid a loss of synchronization during a fault, as shown in Fig. 16.

Figure 16: PLL.

The grid frequency is frozen during fault duration considering the fault detection signal. When a fault occurs the PLL cannot follow the grid angle. Therefore the large difference between the estimated and the real frequency of the grid produces big variations of the angle. When the fault ends, the synchronism between the converter and the grid could bring undesired dynamics or even a loss of synchronisation. Furthermore, an anti-windup control is added to ensure that dynamics are not affected by the accumulated error of the PI when the PLL frequency is frozen.

4.4. DC Voltage Control Modification

The active power reference values are defined as zero during a fault, to ensure that all the available current is used to maintain the DC bus stability. The active power reference value of each AC port $P_{0,i}^*$ is zero, when *Fault* signal is active.

5. Validation of MC Control

The normal and fault operation of the MC is validated in a LV distribution grid. The studied system has two feeders with the MC connected at the end of them and loads are not represented, as shown in Fig. 17. A common distribution grid is studied because it is more challenging in terms of control than a system with two separated grids. Balanced and unbalanced faults are analysed, especially focusing on the scenarios where the AC ports connected to the distribution grid are affected by a common AC fault, which represents a critical situation as was also analyzed in [30].

Table 1: Case study parameters

Parameter	Value
Nominal AC grid voltage, V_{ac-N}	400 V
Nominal port port power, S_{c-N}	300 kVA
Nominal DC bus voltage of MC, V_{dc-N}	800 V
Short Circuit Ratio, SCR	10
AC port active power references, P_1^*, P_2^*	0.66 p.u., -0.66 p.u.
AC port reactive power references, Q_1^*, Q_2^*	0.33 p.u., -0.33 p.u.
DC voltage reference, V_{dc}^*	1 p.u.
Battery active power reference, P_3^*	0.33 p.u.
DC load active power references, P_4^*, P_5^*	-0.066 p.u., -0.066 p.u.
Equivalent impedance, R_{eq}, L_{eq}	1 p.u., 2.58 e-4 p.u.
Grid impedance, R_g, L_g	$0.85R_{eq}, 0.85L_{eq}$
Feeder 1 impedance, R_1, L_1	$0.15R_{eq}, 0.15L_{eq}$
Feeder 2 impedance, R_2, L_2	$0.15R_{eq}, 0.15L_{eq}$
Converter impedance, R_l, L_l	0.01 p.u., 0.2 p.u.

Three scenarios have been studied in order to validate MC operation in normal and fault conditions:

- Scenario 1: 3-port converter with two AC ports connected to the feeders and one DC port connected to a battery (Fig. 17.a).
- Scenario 2: 5-port converter with two AC ports connected to the feeders, one DC port connected to a battery, one DC port connected to a DC load and one DC load directly connected to the DC bus (Fig. 17.b).
- Scenario 3: 3-port converter with two AC ports connected to the feeders and one DC port unavailable (Fig. 17.a).

The faults could be near AC ports (between the port and the line impedances (F_2)) or in the interconnection point of lines 1 and 2 (between transformer impedances and grid impedance (F_1)).

Figure 17: Scenarios considered for MC control validation.

The three scenarios have been tested with the same conditions. The references of the active and reactive powers are changed 0.2 p.u. its initial value to validate that the controller is well-designed in normal operation. Two fault locations are studied: F_1 and F_2 . F_1 represents a fault far from AC ports, while F_2 is a fault near AC port 2 (T_2). Therefore, F_2 is a deep fault for port 2 (T_2) and a mid-range fault for port 1 (T_1). Testing of balanced and unbalanced faults ensures that the MC structure presented in this article is validated in any AC fault condition. Faults last 0.2 s in all the scenarios. The unbalanced faults shown in this article are between phase A and the ground (Type B) [47]. The MC control has also been validated for all the other types of unbalanced faults but the results are not included in this paper due to lack of space. A time domain simulation is done with the following events:

- t=1.5 s variation of DC load power (Scenario 2) or battery disconnection (Scenario 3).
- t=2.5 s variation of MC power.
- t=3 s application of balanced fault (F_1).
- t=4.5 s application of balanced fault (F_2).
- t=6 s application of unbalanced fault (F_1).

5.1. Scenario 1: 3-ports MC with Battery

This scenario is the simplest one, as a battery maintains the DC voltage stability.

a) Voltage results in Scenario 1.

b) Power results in Scenario 1.

c) Current results in Scenario 1.

d) α_i parameters in Scenario 1.

Figure 18: Scenario 1 results.

In this scenario, as the battery is available during all the simulations, the α_3 parameter of the DC port remains 1 following Algorithm 1. Therefore, the controller works as a leader-follower strategy in which the DC port is the leader port. In normal operation, the MC follows the P and Q references at the AC ports and the battery from the DC port compensates the required P and regulates the DC voltage, as observed in Fig. 18.a and Fig. 18.b (period before 2.5 s). When the reference is changed the battery changes its active power, adapting its value to ensure stability of the DC voltage.

In the case of balanced fault F_1 (from 3 s to 3.2 s), the AC voltage in both ports is close to zero. The AC ports reduce the active power while injecting positive reactive current. Also, the battery keeps DC voltage regulation modifying the injected P. AC ports prioritize the reactive current as the battery is

available and injects the required active power. Reactive current saturates at its maximum value, however, as AC voltages are zero, reactive power is zero. Negative currents remain zero in steady state, except in the transients between normal and fault conditions, where negative currents present a disturbance due to the notch filter used for the sequence decoupling.

At 4.5 s a balanced fault occurs near port 2 (F_2). AC voltages show that port 2 has an AC voltage near 0, but port 1 has an AC voltage of almost 0.3 p.u.. As with F_1 , the battery maintains the DC bus stability. In this case, port 1 still has some voltage, so its reactive power is different from 0.

When the unbalanced fault at the interconnection point (F_1) occurs (6 s) the behaviour is equivalent to the case with the balanced fault. The positive AC peak voltage sag is 1/3 of its nominal value, as only 1 phase is lost. Furthermore, negative AC voltage appears due to the unbalance. Active and reactive power show 100 Hz oscillations during the fault, as the negative reference currents are defined as 0[47]. When a 3-port MC with a charged battery is connected, it is concluded that the system behaves as designed.

5.2. Scenario 2: 5-ports MC with Battery, DC load connected to a DC port and DC load connected to the DC bus

This scenario is presented to validate that the MC control structure presented in this paper can be extended to N number of ports.

a) Voltage results in Scenario 2.

b) Power results in Scenario 2.

c) Current results in Scenario 2.

d) α_i parameters in Scenario 2.

Figure 19: Scenario 2 results.

Fig. 19 illustrates the results for Scenario 2, where the battery ensures a continuous power supply to the connected loads. At 1.5 s, a change in DC active power is introduced to the load connected to the DC port. In addition, the load directly connected to the DC bus is not controllable. Therefore, any variation in DC voltage results in a corresponding change in the load's active power.

Consequently, if DC available power supply systems exist, adding ports does not deteriorate the normal and fault operation of the MC.

5.3. Scenario 3: 3-ports MC without Battery

In this scenario, the battery cannot regulate the DC bus voltage during all the test. DC load consumes active power, so it cannot be considered a DC power supply system. Following Algorithm 1, the α_i parameter of the DC load

is zero. In this way, the system ensures that active power is always maintained constant, therefore the DC load is isolated from AC faults. It should be noted that the battery must have sufficient available energy capacity.

a) Voltage results in scenario 3.

b) Power results in Scenario 3.

c) Current results in Scenario 3.

d) α_i parameters in Scenario 3.

Figure 20: Scenario 3 results.

In this scenario battery is available until 1.5 s, consequently, AC ports are responsible for maintaining the DC bus voltage constant. Fig. 20.d shows that the α_i parameter of the battery is 1 until 1.5 s.

In normal operation without a battery, both AC/DC ports follow the P and Q references, while controlling the DC voltage. Both ports are equal, consequently, the value of α_i is 0.5.

The most critical condition occurs at 3 s when a deep balanced fault near the common grid occurs (F_1). α_i parameter is 0.5 in both ports because both ports' PCC have a voltage equal to 0. During the fault, the active current is prioritized in both ports as there are no DC exchange systems and the same AC voltage is seen (almost 0 V). The voltage v_{DC} cannot be controlled, but by prioritizing the active current in both ports the DC voltage reduction is limited

as much as possible.

At 4.5 s, a deep balanced fault appears near port 2 (F_2). AC voltages are different in both ports, having port 1 a bigger value than port 2. Following Algorithm 1, port 1 has an α_i parameter of 1. During the fault, port 2 prioritizes the reactive current. In port 1 the active current is prioritized, so the necessary current is given to ensure the system's stability. All the remaining current is available for reactive current. Port 1 consumes reactive power during the fault near its nominal value, due to the remaining available reactive current. As with the other scenarios, negative currents are zero when the fault starts and ends.

When the unbalanced fault at the interconnection point (F_1) occurs at 6 s, the DC bus voltage can be maintained by both AC ports. In both cases, the ports prioritize the active current, which maintains the DC bus voltage stable. The remaining current is used as reactive current. As with the other scenarios, the negative sequence current is zero except at the beginning and end of the fault. The active and reactive powers during the fault oscillate again at 100 Hz. From the different tests, it is concluded that the controller is also validated in this scenario.

6. MC Control Strategies Comparison

The main characteristics of the control strategies found in the literature and the proposed control are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Control strategies comparison.

	[20]	[30]	[28]	[31]	[6]	[32]	Proposed
N-ports	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
DC ports	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
v_{DC} tracking	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
AC ports	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Unbalanced AC grids	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
AC FRT at N ports	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓

Regarding port flexibility, both the Leader-Follower approach [20] and the VMM method [30] are not easily scalable to systems with a large number of ports. In contrast, the remaining reviewed strategies support more modular and scalable configurations. As demonstrated in Section 5, the proposed centralized control ensures scalability, allowing the addition of N ports while maintaining the desired dynamic behavior.

All reviewed strategies are capable of managing both AC and DC ports, with the exception of the approach in [31], which has only been studied for DC grid applications. The topology and control proposed in this work support AC and DC ports, with DC ports being either directly connected to the DC bus or interfaced via a DC-DC converter.

As discussed in Section 1, droop and VMM control schemes cannot achieve precise DC voltage tracking, as demonstrated in [28, 30]. The proposed centralized control guarantees DC voltage tracking in all cases, except during severe AC faults that occur near the main grid. Other reviewed methods in the literature also provide effective DC voltage tracking under normal and some abnormal conditions.

Among the compared works, only the method proposed in [30] explicitly addresses FRT capabilities at all available AC ports. Section 5 demonstrates that centralized control can also ensure FRT across all ports, as a consequence of the modifications detailed in Section 4.

Finally, none of the reviewed strategies have evaluated performance under unbalanced AC grid conditions. In contrast, the proposed centralized control can effectively manage unbalances, as demonstrated in Section 5, by defining the controller in the qd^{+-} reference frame.

7. Conclusion

Multiport converters (MCs) are a key technology for future distribution grids. This paper proposed a flexible control structure for MCs that supports integration of an N number of AC and DC ports. A centralized DC voltage control architecture has been developed to ensure accurate DC bus regulation under normal conditions, while maintaining robustness against AC faults. The control algorithm prioritizes DC power supplies for DC voltage regulation and shifts control to AC ports when DC power supplies are unavailable. Designed using a linear system model and pole placement, the controller achieves zero steady-state error in DC voltage tracking. To address FRT requirements, the controller has been modified to provide a robust response regardless of fault location, and includes a fault current injection mechanism for support in line with grid codes and standards.

Validations have been addressed in a scenario with 3,5-port MCs. In normal operation, MCs guarantee correct tracking of the power reference signals. FRT capabilities are ensured for deep faults on ports, except when a deep fault affects all AC ports, in which case DC bus voltage cannot be controlled because no active power is available from the ports.

Appendix A. Optimization constraints

The disturbance rejection constraint is formulated as the following optimization problem

$$\|W_S(jw)S(jw, x)\|_\infty < 1, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where w is the frequency of the disturbance, x the parameters of the tuned controller, $S(jw, x)$ the sensitivity function, and W_S the frequency weighting function derived from the specified attenuation profile. The W_S function is defined to attenuate 40 dB at 0 Hz (frequency of the active power references).

To address settling time constraints, the optimization problem is formulated as

$$\min_x \|W_S(s)S(s, x)\|_\infty, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where x are the parameters of the tuned controller, $S(s, x)$ the sensitivity function, and W_S the frequency weighting function derived from the soft specifications of settling time. W_S is defined as:

$$W_S(s) = \frac{sM + \omega_b A}{s + \omega_b},$$

where:

- ω_b is the tracking bandwidth, which is $\frac{2}{t_s}$,
- t_s is the settling time,
- M specifies the maximum tracking error across all frequencies,
- A is the maximum steady-state tracking error.

The specification of the damping ratio is addressed through the following optimization problem

$$\min_x \|T(s, x)\|_\infty, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $T(s, x)$ represents the complementary sensitivity function, and x are the parameters of the tuned controller. Achieving an ∞ -norm of $T(s, x)$ equal to 1 corresponds to a damping ratio of approximately 0.707. The optimization aims to identify parameters that result in an ∞ -norm close to 1, ensuring suitable damping behavior.

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